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of Medical Research

Developing and translating participant and consent information for ancestry groups underrepresented in genomics research

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Executive summary

Many Australians who are not of European ancestry are underrepresented in genomics research and datasets including those of African, Asian, Middle Eastern and Oceanian descent. One barrier to the participation of culturally and linguistically diverse (CALD) Australians in medical research is the lack of accessible participant information and consent materials in community languages. In this report, we describe the development of a modular set of materials translated into ten languages to support Australian population and clinical genomics researchers to include greater numbers of participants from underrepresented groups in their research.

In this report, we outline the steps we took in the development of these materials. We first undertook a landscape review of literature discussing culturally-appropriate and understandable consent materials in genomics. We also gathered examples of existing participant information materials available worldwide. These informed a draft of a plain English version of the participant information and consent materials that was critiqued as part of a consultation with genomics researchers and cross-cultural communication experts. Experts made terminology recommendations and noted the need to balance simple language with ethics committee requirements. These plain English materials were then translated into ten languages of communities for whom addressing underrepresentation in clinical and population genomics research was determined to be a priority: Arabic, Dari, Farsi, Fijian, Hazaragi, Samoan, Tagalog, Tongan, Urdu, and Vietnamese.

Partnering with a cross-cultural communication agency who oversaw the translations, we gathered feedback from translators to gain insight into terminology and phrasing that presented translation challenges, as well as to understand the translation decisions they had made. With the translators, we conducted ten focus groups with bilingual speakers of the different language communities, asking for participants' feedback on the plain English version, the content of the materials, and translations. Overall, community members appreciated the simple explanations but identified a key tension between length and depth in participant information

materials. Participants reinforced the need to consider approaches beyond the standard textual presentation.

We then revised the plain English version and translations based on both translators' and community members' advice. Words were added to the glossary to facilitate translation, including the term 'risk', which had a much more negative meaning in several languages than intended. The materials were divided into segments to allow researchers to assemble their own research participant information and consent documents. The text was audio recorded, and both text and audio files will be provided to researchers in a modular format under a Creative Commons licence.

We provide recommendations for the development and translation of participant and consent materials for ancestry groups underrepresented in genomics research (See Box 1). This project has reinforced the importance of community consultation in ensuring translations were accurately communicating researchers' intended messages. Our process highlighted the value of working closely with translators and consulting community members, and the need for innovation in effectively engaging underrepresented groups.

Recommendations

- Consult community members about content and translations
- Work closely with translators; brief them on the materials and provide them with guidelines.
- Keep participant materials as short and simple as possible but be precise
- Structure materials to cater for different information needs
- Make content more digestible and engaging using stories, visual imagery, and multimedia
- Attend to the tone of the document
- Be aware of how presentation of risks may overshadow benefits of taking part in genomic research
- Consider what needs to be in place beyond the participant materials for people to engage with them
- Be aware of practical considerations of presenting translated audio and written materials online

Introduction

Internationally, genomics research cohorts and reference datasets lack diversity with an overwhelming overrepresentation of people of European descent (Fatumo et al. 2022; Sirugo, Williams, and Tishkoff 2019). Given Australians' very diverse ancestral backgrounds, unless active steps are taken to address this problem, current rapid advances in genetic medicine will not benefit many Australian culturally and linguistically diverse (CALD) communities. One potential barrier to increasing the representation of CALD communities is the lack of suitable genomics participant information materials in plain English and community languages. In this project, we aimed to address this gap in materials to create a resource for Australian genomics researchers that would support them to include greater numbers of underrepresented CALD groups in their research. The design of the project was based on a literature review informing the Centre for Population Genomics' (CPG) flagship program (OurDNA) that addresses the underrepresentation of many Australian ancestry groups in genomics research (Croy, Ambegaokar, and MacArthur 2021).

Australians self-identify with over 300 ancestries and 23 percent speak a language other than English at home (Australian Bureau of Statistics 2022) In the health sector, this diversity of languages requires clinicians and researchers to ensure their communication accurately reaches all Australians. Yet there are few translated genomics informational materials in Australia, even as genomics increasingly becomes a standard part of health care. As the genomics sector increasingly recognises the urgency of addressing the underrepresentation of Australians who are not of European ancestry in genomics research and datasets, and more and more genetic research projects seek to address this gap, the availability of culturally aligned and language-appropriate informational and consent materials is crucial.

Genomics research requires the communication of complex ideas, and this has often resulted in the production of lengthy participant information and consent documents. Researchers recognise that materials that overwhelm participants are a barrier to informed consent and meaningful decision-making (Wilbanks 2018; Kraft and Doerr

2018). Due to the fast-changing nature of genomics, and the volume of information that must be conveyed, researchers have also noted that participants may require information at different points in time (Bromley et al. 2020), that researchers might consider tiered or layered consent models to move towards appropriately, rather than fully, informed consent (Koplin et al. 2022).

To reach a broad range of community members, information materials need to cater to different levels of literacy. The Centre for Culture, Ethnicity, and Health (Centre for Culture, Ethnicity & Health 2015) recommends that materials developed for CALD communities be pitched at a grade 4-6 level, broken up into short sentences, avoiding the use of jargon.

The lack of participant information materials in community languages is known to be a barrier to CALD Australians' participation in medical research (Low, Barcenilla-Wong, and Brijnath 2019; Smith et al. 2018). Translation of health and medical information is a complex process and translation on its own may not be enough to ensure that intended messages are effectively communicated. The experience of communication COVID-19 health information to migrant communities in Australia has demonstrated that consulting community members about translations of complex information can ensure that people received the messages that health communicators intend (Wild et al. 2021).

In this project, we developed a generic set of genomics research participant information and consent materials in plain English and associated translations to be made freely available to researchers under a Creative Commons licence. These materials are presented in modular form for researchers to be able to assemble their own participant information materials and will be available at <https://populationgenomics.org.au/> from the middle of 2024. We translated the materials into ten community languages. Our intention is for the English version to be easily translatable into many other languages to support researchers to include greater numbers of participants from underrepresented communities to take part in genetics and genomics research.

We prioritised ten languages of CALD groups needed in both clinical and population research. To prioritise, we looked at a combination of the gap in population genomic data, size of the population in Australia, and groups that are seen in clinical practice based on a small survey of clinicians (CPG Reports 2022). We also ensured that we included groups from all of the most underrepresented regions in genomics datasets. These regions include Oceania, East Africa, Middle East and North Africa, and Southeast Asia. The ten priority languages are Arabic, Dari, Farsi, Fijian, Hazaragi, Samoan, Tagalog, Tongan, Urdu, and Vietnamese.

Approach to developing participant information and consent materials

Step 1: Drafting plain English

The participant information materials were informed by existing examples and templates in practice and the literature (See Table 1) found through a literature scan.

Table 1 Existing participant information examples and templates

Clinical consent fact sheet, Australian Genomics	https://www.australiangenomics.org.au/tools-and-resources/research-consent-forms/
Australian Genomics Research PICF	https://www.australiangenomics.org.au/tools-and-resources/research-consent-forms/
ACI (clinical) consent forms & information (NSW)	https://aci.health.nsw.gov.au/networks/clinical-genetics/resources/testing-consent-forms
National statement on ethical conduct in human research	https://www.nhmrc.gov.au/about-us/publications/national-statement-ethical-conduct-human-research-2007-updated-2018#toc__826
NHGRI & NIH informed consent resources	https://www.genome.gov/about-genomics/policy-issues/Informed-Consent https://sharing.nih.gov/data-management-and-sharing-policy/protecting-participant-privacy-when-sharing-scientific-data/considerations-for-obtaining-informed-consent
Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH)	https://www.ga4gh.org/document/consent-clauses-for-genomic-research/

Additional resources in research were consulted, including publications with model consent clauses (Nguyen et al. 2019), new consent approaches (Koplin et al. 2022) and consent clauses developed for clinical diagnostics (Riggs et al. 2019).

Once an outline for the materials was developed, text was drafted by an interdisciplinary group of genetic counsellors, clinical researchers and educators. The team agreed on the topics to cover in the materials to meet the requirements from the NHMRC Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research. These included coverage of: benefits and risks of genetic and genomic testing, genetic variants and relevant conditions, return of results, reanalysis of genetic information,

data security and access, and practical considerations including who funded the research, implications of withdrawing from the study at different stages of the research and the potential costs to participants. Topics included genetic research-specific information covering a range of research types, as well as general explanations about health and medical research. The final sections included:

- What is health research?
- What is genetic and genomic research?
- What are the benefits and risks of taking part in this research?
- What happens to my information if I take part in research? (storage, data sharing, people)

The materials were drafted in simple English. We used vignettes to convey concepts relevant to returning different types of results. (see Box 1 for example).

Sarah took part in research looking at the genetic information of young, healthy people. Sarah receives a call from a genetic health professional and finds out that she is one of the few people receiving a result from the study. The researchers found that she has a gene variant that increases her chances of developing breast and ovarian cancer at a young age. Sarah has regular breast screening and is receiving medical care to reduce her chances of developing cancer.

Box 1 Example of vignette used to explain return of results

Step 2: Expert consultation

Once we had a draft of the materials, we invited a group of genomics researchers and cross-cultural communication experts to provide feedback on the materials. The experts were able to provide feedback in several ways:

- providing documents for direct markup,
- a short survey
- attending a facilitated consultation meeting

Fifteen experts attended the meeting and/or provided in-depth feedback on the materials. The feedback was summarised and reviewed by the project team to inform document revisions. Cross-cultural communication experts recommended further simplification of terminology, shortening of sentences, greater use of bullet points and the inclusion of a glossary that they noted was essential for translators. Genomics researchers raised concerns about whether the simple explanations would be too little to satisfy ethical review, and whether the phrasing could cause difficulties for data access committees. They also gave recommendations for preferred terms to use in the materials.

Additional feedback came from applying these documents to CPG's flagship program OurDNA's consent pathway and ethical approval.

Step 3: Translation

CultureVerse, a multicultural communications and marketing consultancy, oversaw the translation of the materials, engaging translators experienced in health and medical translations. The materials were translated by a main translator and then checked by a second translator, or 'checker'. CultureVerse gathered feedback from translators on terms that did not have equivalents in their languages, challenges that they experienced in translating the materials, and translation decisions that they had to make.

Words that translators reported did not have equivalents in their language included words related to genetics (e.g. chromosome, DNA, gene, genetics, genome, and genomics), other medical terms (e.g. biomedical, cancer, familial hypercholesterolemia, and tissue), as well as words commonly used in research (e.g. for-profit, computer, ethics, and project). Translators dealt with these in several ways, depending on what was conventional in their language, including:

- Transliteration of an approximate pronunciation of the English word in-language
- Use of the English word

- Definition of the English word, used repeatedly
- Definition of the English word once, then use of the English word subsequently

Translators noted challenges in translating some terms that the genomics experts we consulted had explicitly requested. 'Blood relatives' was translated as:

- 'relatives who are related to you by blood' (Arabic);
- 'people related by blood' or 'people of the same bloodline' (Vietnamese).

Researchers requested the term 'health condition' to avoid reference to disease or sickness, but this was not always possible to avoid (e.g. 'a disease/sickness' in Vietnamese). Some translators noted that the very simple language used could sometimes sacrifice precision for translation. For example, in their feedback to us, the Samoan translator noted that they found the English version 'too simple and general' which made the translation into Samoan difficult. Similarly, in a discussion about the use of the word 'money' instead of 'funding', the Arabic translator suggested that the simple language could sometimes be 'too simple'.

Step 4: Focus groups with community members

We conducted 10 focus groups with community members who were bilingual in English and Arabic, Dari, Farsi, Fijian, Hazaragi, Samoan, Tagalog, Tongan, Urdu, or Vietnamese (See Table 2). We recruited bilingual community members so that they would be able to simultaneously provide advice about the translations as well as the text in English. Participants were recruited through purposive and snowball sampling through community organisations and multicultural sector networks. Participants were over 18 years of age, bilingual in English and the community language, and willing to read through the materials. The focus groups were conducted in person in either Sydney (3) or Melbourne (3), or online (4) with between 5 and 10 participants per focus group including the translator. Participants received a \$100 voucher for their time.

The focus group discussion was divided into two parts. The first part was conducted in English and focused on the content of the materials. In this part of the discussion, we aimed to learn from community members how the materials could be improved as well as how they thought community members might respond to the information. We asked participants what was clear and useful in the materials and what required clarification or more information. We also asked them what they thought would be appealing and encouraging to community members and what might make community members uncertain or discouraged from taking part in genomics research.

The second part was conducted in language, facilitated by a translator who gathered feedback about the translation. Translators were either the original translator, the checker, or, where neither were available, a third translator who was not involved in translating the materials. In the case of the Fijian focus group, our community contact recommended that we engage a third translator to ensure that participants would not be restricted in providing feedback out of respect for the translator. Translators were invited to contribute to the conversation about the content of the materials as community members themselves. Translators noted participants' feedback on the translations and summarised and relayed recommended changes to the English version to the project team.

The focus group discussion about the content of the materials was audio recorded and transcribed. The project team also took notes during the focus groups and a summary of recommended changes to the English version were immediately relayed to the team responsible for drafting the materials. Three project team members (RS, SP, and SC) then analysed the focus group data relating to the content of the materials by sorting the data into broad categories, first trial coding a sample of the data to ensure agreement between coders. These broad categories included participant feedback on presentation of the information (e.g. readability, accessibility, understanding, and volume of information), reactions to the content (e.g. perceptions, concerns, motivations to take part in research) and recommendations for improving the materials (e.g. addressing concerns and making materials more engaging). RS and SP then conducted second-round coding to describe the data in

each of these broader categories with SC reviewing the coding. The team met regularly to discuss progress to ensure consistency in coding. The focus group findings on community preferences for receiving genomics research participant information are presented below.

Table 2 Focus groups with bilingual community members

Language community	Number of participants	Location	Translator
Arabic	6	Sydney	Original
Dari (Afghan)	7	Melbourne	Original
Farsi (Iranian)	6	Online	Original
Fijian	5	Online	Third*
Hazaragi (Hazara)	8	Online	Checker
Samoan	6	Melbourne	Third*
Tagalog	6	Sydney	Original
Tongan	8	Melbourne	Checker
Urdu (Pakistani)	7	Online	Original
Vietnamese	10	Sydney	Checker

*Translator facilitating discussion was not translator or checker of the materials

Step 5: Refining plain English and translations

Greater specificity

Many of the changes to the English version involved increasing the specificity language to remove ambiguity for translators in how they should translate the text as well as providing clarification for community members. For example, we replaced some words that were initially chosen as a way of simply conveying a concept e.g. 'money' rather than 'funding', 'answers' rather than 'findings'.

In the revised version, we used the more precise 'ancestry community' rather than just 'community' as participants in the Samoan focus group noted that there were many communities that one might be a part of. We also changed 'sample' to 'biological sample' as our Vietnamese focus group participants and translator noted that the word 'sample' on its own was meaningless in Vietnamese. Translators were not at liberty to add this clarification on their own accord. At the request of the Arabic

translator, we avoided multiple uses of the word 'share' that was in the initial draft (e.g. share information, share an ancestry).

Added definitions to the glossary

We found that the word 'risk' did not translate well in several languages including Arabic, Hazaragi, and Vietnamese, having a much heavier meaning and a greater sense of inevitability than intended. We dealt with this by including a definition of 'risk and benefit' in the glossary and defined risk to capture the idea of chance. We also included an instruction to translators in the guidelines to use a word that captures the sense of chance.

Other words that we added to the glossary included:

- ancestry community (see explanation above)
- ancestry forum
- Database
- biological sample (see explanation above)

Translation changes needed based on participant feedback

Translators made changes to wording and phrasing based on participants' feedback. An example was the choice of word for 'researcher' in the Samoan translation which, while correct, community members felt had negative connotations and was off-putting.

In many focus groups, participants said that where technical terms were translated, it was helpful to them to have the English words in brackets, or to use the English words throughout once the term had been explained. Participants noted that the English terms for words such as 'genetics' and 'DNA' would be more familiar to the community in Australia. As well, participants noted that instances where the

definition of technical terms was repeated wherever the term appeared in the text made the text long and unwieldy.

In some cases, participants suggested that while the English version was written in simple, plain English, the translated version was not in simple language. We added a guideline to translators specifying that the translation should be in simple accessible language. We also requested that translators attend to the readability of the document as the requirement that translators stay close to the text through word for word translation made the translations clunky in some instances. See [Appendix 1](#) for the guidelines provided to translators.

Community members' feedback on content of participant information materials

Simple explanations were appreciated

Participants appreciated the simple language used in the materials that we gave them. Participants noted that the document was easy to understand, and that it used words that were 'very simple' (Fijian focus group), and that they were 'straightforward to follow and well structured' (Hazaragi focus group). One participant in the Arabic focus group noted the simple materials would attract not just 'intellectual people' who would usually be inclined to take part in research, but a broader demographic of community members.

The document in English [is], as you said, [in] plain English, it was very easy to understand.

(Farsi focus group participant)

A number of participants noted at the same time that while they found the materials easy to understand, some in the community may nevertheless still find the topic of genetic research difficult to grasp. They anticipated possible challenges for older people in their communities: 'if you explain it to our elders, it can get difficult.' (Tongan focus group), or those in their communities whose education had been disrupted:

Because of using a lot of jargons and technical like genomics expressions, sometimes it can be a little bit difficult in my opinion for an average Afghan person, having in my mind that the majority in the community here are not highly educated

(Dari focus group participant)

The word 'genomics' was explained once but not used otherwise in the participant information materials. A Farsi focus group participant who works with refugee communities that access Farsi-language resources noted that even words like 'database' might be overly technical. We added a definition of 'database' to the glossary. Participants pointed out, however, that text-based information alone may not be enough to support some in their communities to understand genetic research participation.

Brevity was very important to the participants

Across all focus groups, participants commented on the length of the document. While we explained that the materials were not designed to be used altogether and that projects would need to select parts of the materials as relevant, we consistently heard that the length of the materials was something that needed to be attended to. A participant in the Arabic focus group suggested having a summary of the materials as 'nobody will read this much' while a Vietnamese focus group participant said: 'The more talk you do, the more you confuse people.'

Participants suggested structuring the material in a way that allowed readers to extract the main points quickly:

We can have some sort of guidance at the start of the document that highlights the main points, like a guide or summary to help the reader or infographics, so the reader can decide if this document is for me to read or not.

(Farsi focus group participant)

Some participants wanted more information about particular topics such as greater detail about privacy and data security (Arabic focus group) or greater explanation of why their particular community was being invited to take part (Tagalog focus group). These details would be specific to different projects and were thus not covered in these base modular materials. A number of participants also noted that they enjoyed learning about an area that they had previously been unfamiliar with. They suggested providing opportunities for people to learn more about different topics if they wanted by providing links to further information.

Participants appreciated stories and suggested use of visual imagery and multimedia to engage participants

We made use of vignettes to convey the idea of the return of results and participants said that they found these very useful (see Box 1). Participants liked the 'real life examples' (Tagalog focus group) that were effective in 'personalising' the concept to illustrate what a community member 'would go through' (Tongan focus group). A participant in the Urdu focus group described the examples of discovering a hereditary cancer or receiving information about reproductive planning to be 'encouraging'. They asked us to use more stories like these to convey other topics such as the benefit of taking part in research. A participant in the Fijian focus group suggested providing 'a scenario where this type of research has actually helped a family'. Researchers using these generic materials could consider how similar vignettes could be used to convey ideas specific to their projects.

Participants also suggested that we avoid presenting people with walls of text. They suggested breaking up the text with images and graphics and considering alternatives to text such as videos. A participant in our Urdu focus group suggested having a 'visual narrative' which would 'improve the format of the document and make it more friendly to use and understand'. Others noted that people absorbed information in different ways. Some people were 'visual learners' and would 'need to see it' (Tongan focus group).

Many participants suggested that videos would be a good way to communicate the information contained in the materials. A participant in our Hazaragi focus group noted that a video would be a good way to introduce the document. It would 'spark' people's interest and 'inspire people to read the document'. This could be something that researchers consider in addition to the text-based participant information they assemble using these base materials.

Participants thought benefits of research participation needed to be emphasised

A consistent theme in the focus group discussions was the need for the benefits of taking part in genetics research to be emphasised. The benefit for 'future generations' was something that participants found extremely compelling and encouraged us to ensure that this message was clear in the materials and any conversations with communities.

For us the structure from the beginning should have the benefit first, what is the benefit for participating in this so people will be interested.

(Vietnamese focus group participant)

Genetics, DNA, and these things, they're not very familiar for people, especially for our community. If at first we talk and make something clear, what is genetics [used] for, ...what [are] the benefits for the future, it will be very good.

(Dari focus group participant)

Participants raised the question of the presentation of risk and some questioned the extent to which laying out all possible risks was necessary. One participant from our Tagalog focus group noted said:

'Unknown risk'. Why do we have to put it there?...There are always things that are unknowable. It just triggers a signal. Gives a red signal. You might be hiding something, you know?

This participant suggested taking a risk-based assessment to decision making about what needed to be presented. Another participant wondered if the presentation of risks would completely overshadow the benefits of taking. He noted that he was not encouraging deception, but said:

In my head, this is an awesome thing to do. It helps everyone, it helps the community, it helps the researchers. So there could be some risks. But by making all these risks crystal clear, would you create a lot of turn-off for people?...are you still wanting participation?

(Farsi focus group participant)

Other Australian research on consent in medical research generally has similarly found that consumers recommend ensuring that the presentation of risks does not overshadow the benefits of taking part (Symons 2023). The challenging nature of the presentation of the risks of genomics research and the potential to discourage already underrepresented groups is a topic that would warrant further investigation.

Attend to the tone of the document

In some focus groups, participants noted that it was important to attend to the tone of the document to not put members of their community off from participating in genetics research. In a discussion during the Arabic focus group about the potential that people might be required to disclose results of genetic testing, particularly to insurers ('You may have to share genetic information you get back from a research project'), participants noted that statements that someone was required to do something could be considered intimidating. Instead, one participant suggested

having a 'gentle statement about it to remind them of their obligation, but not in a scary way'.

The focus group participants discussed the statement, acknowledging that gentler wording would not convey the potential requirement to share information. Members of the project team similarly considered whether it was possible to change the wording and concluded that the discomfort was with the fact of the requirement rather than the way it was worded.

Participants in our Samoan focus group similarly discussed how the tone of the document would have an impact on community members' willingness to take part in medical research noting that many community members are reluctant to engage with the health system. One participant suggested using language that foregrounded participant autonomy and agency and focused on well-being. 'Instead of focusing on taking the blood, having the saliva, having you know the actual process of doing the test', this participant suggested focusing on the purpose of the research being about the health and well-being of their families. With the right language, she noted, 'The anxiety can come down a little bit faster'.

Researchers using these materials could consider how to balance what participation involves with description of why community members might want to take part. If researchers are working with specific communities, this could be tailored to them. Researchers should also consider whether indirect rather than direct communication styles may be more culturally appropriate (Miracle, Yeol Chang, and Taylor 1992).

Community members' recommendations for developing materials to engage underrepresented groups in genomics research

Beyond participant information materials

In addition to commenting on participant information and consent materials, participants had many suggestions for how to involve their communities in genetics research that went beyond the scope of the materials. People were interested in reading about how this research would be of benefit to their communities and wanted to learn more. Participants felt that once members of their communities learned about the relevance of genetics research to them and the benefit to their communities, they would be open to participating.

...if you talk about benefits of something, I am pretty sure everyone will participate. And what I found here is this topic, it says future health issues that has treatment that sort of thing. If that [is] elaborated more [and] explained properly to people, I am pretty sure you will have many more participants. That's my opinion.

(Dari focus group participant)

They noted that genomics would be something that was completely new to community members, and that education resources that would help community members become more familiar with genetics and genomics would be beneficial. Participants requested education sessions, general educational videos, talanoa (conversation) sessions (Tongan focus group). One participant in the Fijian focus group noted:

If there's no conversation, ...it's just going to be another material that everyone's going to read, but we don't really feel connected to it.

(Fijian focus group participant)

This comment resonates with research that has found that relying on text alone to convey genomic research participant information to ethnic minority communities is inadequate and that these materials should be accompanied by options for face-to-face meetings and conversation (Tekola et al. 2009; Bukini et al. 2020; Prictor et al. 2020).

Indicate to community members that the materials are for them

Participants noted that community-specific elements would attract the attention of community members. This included language. A Samoan focus group participant, referring to her mother, said:

...[If] she sees something that is in her language across the room, she's going to gravitate towards it, she's going to read it...

This participant also suggested that Pasifika designs would attach community members to the materials. In many focus groups, participants said that imagery of 'people who look like us' would be helpful in engaging members of their community. One participant in our Hazaragi focus group said:

I would have smiled or loved it to open the file and see a smiley little Hazara girl...anything that gives Hazara specific vibes to the reader.

(Hazaragi focus group participant)

This feedback suggests that, if seeking to engage particular communities, researchers could develop community-specific imagery in their promotional materials. Projects seeking to recruit from the general population inclusively could also consider imagery that represents multicultural communities. Based on focus group participants' recommendations, we have developed a set of accompanying images depicting diverse participants, clinicians, and scientists that researchers may wish to use in their own projects (See [Appendix 2](#)).

Developing compelling messaging

Participants had many suggestions about how to develop messaging that would appeal to community members. Participants noted that to encourage community members to take part, researchers needed to talk in terms of what people knew and were familiar with. They suggested 'making it personal':

 speak[ing] in terms of how the community thinks...for example, a number of your relatives have experienced the same health problems in the past years.

 (Tagalog focus group participant)

This could also be done by referencing common health concerns like diabetes that many people would be concerned about:

 The popular cases. So everybody knows every single person has diabetes. So use real life examples to relate it back to them.

 (Tongan focus group participant)

Tips for developing participant information materials for groups underrepresented in genomics research

- Keep it short and simple
- Structure materials to cater for different information needs
- Make content more digestible and engaging using stories, visual imagery, and multimedia
- Attend to the tone of the document
- Be aware of how presentation of risks may overshadow benefit of taking part

Tips for engaging underrepresented groups beyond the participant information materials

- Make sure people know materials are for them
- Engage before you want people to read your information materials
- Produce education materials for underrepresented communities
- Develop compelling messages about benefits of taking part

Box 2 Summary of recommendations

Conclusion

The goal of this project has been to develop a generic set of participant information and consent materials that meet the needs of Australian Culturally and Linguistically Diverse communities underrepresented in clinical and population genomics research. The approach that we took in developing these materials has reinforced the importance of working with community members to ensure the suitability of materials for communities. It has highlighted the value of working with both translators and community members to ensure that translations accurately convey what researchers intend. Much of the feedback that we received from community members supports research on genomics research participation with ethnic minority communities internationally, indicating the need to consider modes of communication beyond a text-based consent form. It has also emphasised the need to continue to address the perennial problem of achieving brevity while providing enough depth.

One limitation of our approach was the decision to consult bilingual community members. We took this approach as bilingual community members were able to tell us whether the translations were conveying what the English version was. A downside to this approach is that our bilingual participants may not necessarily be the end users of the translated materials. Future projects adapting our approach may wish to build in consultation with community members who would be reliant on translations.

A challenge that we faced in involving the original translator or checker in the focus groups was that it was difficult for translators to be in a situation where their work was being critiqued. In some groups, participants may have also found it difficult to convey honest critique for fear of offending the translator. We found there to be enormous value in working closely with translators to ensure the accuracy of the translations. Other researchers seeking to involve translators in the process of fine-tuning translated materials may wish to consider how to introduce the intended outcomes of the process to both translator and community member in a way that conveys a sense of partnership in working towards materials that meet the needs of their communities.

While not the intention of this project, our focus groups allowed us to learn how underrepresented communities might respond to invitations to take part in genomics research. The responses we received were encouraging with participants in our focus groups expressing interest in the fact we were working with their communities. In some cases, participants expressed gratitude that their community was being included and that researchers were taking the time to work with community members to ensure that communities' needs were met. Community members had a wealth of information that they were keen to share about how to effectively engage their communities in genomics research. While their recommendations went beyond the scope of this project, this bodes well for genomics researchers seeking to work with communities to address the problem of underrepresentation in genomics research and datasets.

In conclusion, this interdisciplinary, multistage process has enabled the production of a set of plain English and translated participant consent support resources for broad use.

Appendices

Appendix 1: Guidelines for translators

Guidelines for translation of genetic research participant information materials

This is the first time information materials about participating in genomic research have been developed in multiple languages in Australia. By conducting focus groups and asking translators, we have learned some things about what works and what does not work well in translating these materials from English. The following guidelines are intended to support translators to take decisions that will improve the comprehensibility of the content when read in their language.

- We recognise that translators are bound to translate close to the original text to ensure the accuracy of the translation. In some focus groups, participants noted that the literal, word-for-word translation sometimes made the text difficult to understand. We request that translators, if possible, make adjustments that retain the meaning of the English version and improve the comprehension in their language.

For example, the term “body systems” referring, for example, to the cardiovascular system and lymphatic system, etc, should be translated as a phrase having the same meaning in the language, rather than literally translating the two words “body” and “systems” if that does not mean what it does in English.

- The word ‘risk’ was raised in a number of focus groups as being translated into something much more serious and inevitable than intended. The word ‘risk’ is used in the context of medical research participation to note that there is a chance of an event occurring. It is not meant to convey that something bad *will* happen.
 - Where the word in a language conveys the inevitability of serious harm, it would be preferable to choose a different word that more accurately conveys the sense of the word ‘chance’.
- We recognise that words for technical terms may not exist in different languages. Please feel free to use the conventions followed by medical professionals working in your language even if this means retaining the English term. You might find it useful to define the English term once in

translation, and thereafter use the English term.

- Many participants noted that the technical terms in translation were unfamiliar to them and they found it helpful to have the technical terms written in English in brackets.

Appendix 2: Website Images

Figure 1: Images depicting research processes for the webpage design

<p>A group of Australians of diverse backgrounds sitting in a circle listening to researchers present about a project. The image could include thought clouds or speech bubbles with imagery relating to genetics e.g. DNA or proteins.</p>	<p>Researchers sitting together and discussing in a relaxed way. They can be sitting in a circle, one or two characters can be standing up, one character can seem to raise a question, and one can be giving an answer, the rest of the characters can seem to be actively listening and engaging in the conversation.</p>
<p>Diverse medical specialists with some graphic representation of multiple dimensions of health.</p>	<p>Silhouette of person with amplification of DNA, chromosomes, genes etc.</p>

One person at a computer reading through a screen of text.

Different age groups, multi-generational individuals being part of a family, and those families being part of communities.

A female genetic counsellor on the phone with a friendly expression.

Image of a computer with graphics of data and protein on screen.

Different people in lab coats doing research.

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